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A network for simulating pre-colonial migration in the Americas

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Motivation

Existing models of language dispersal are disconnected:

- Continent-scale models make broad assumptions
- Bottom-up models are very non-geographic

Goal: Connect the top-down to individual-level
→ a continent-scale ABM model of languages

- For that: A demographic dispersal model for the Americas
- For that: A network
 - describes locations where people interact over months
 - with distances and population capacities

M. T. P. Coelho et al., doi: 10.31235/osf.io/xqr2u

J. A. Barceló et al., doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-00008-4_10

Building a Demographic Dispersal + Culture ABM

- **Goal:** Can we generate continent-scale **patterns** of language diversity, from combinations of bottom-up models?
 - Patterns, not histories: dynamic equilibrium – climate, ecoregions, max pop cap are fixed
- **Agents = Families** / Bands of hunter-gatherers moving about, consuming resources, growing/shrinking and sometimes splitting in two.
- Interaction based on **seasonal co-occurrence** in interaction radius, depending on cultural similarity and dominance → **Network structure!**

The Network: Overview

Assumptions

- Network is static through time (simulation can have randomness & periodic seasonal patterns)
- Travel time is the major driver for connectivity between people, and is roughly proportional between an individual and a group on a trek
 - includes terrain and navigation (Irmischer&Clarke 2016)
 - includes land cover (Ecoregions2017 → Pozzi&Robinson 2008)
 - includes increasing time to wade ever bigger rivers (GloRiC → Davenport&al. 2017), up to becoming impassable due to depth and water pressure
- Travel by boat at constant speed \pm river flow speed (Schulze&al. 2005)
 - no oceanic currents
 - constant time (\sim 1 day) to switch from walking to boating, including for crossing big rivers

Data and Aggregation

Evaluation

- Reference data hard to come by
 - Suggestions?
- Qualitatively compare a 700 km prehistoric trail (Natchez Trace) with the network's optimal path
 - Some explainable deviations, good enough?
 - Calibration of river crossing Delay ~1 day, quite robust

Natchez, MS

Next steps

- Implement local interactions between different populations
- Simulate, calibrate, analyze:
Can this network be used to generate continent-scale language patterns?

Summary

Big Assumptions

ABM of hunter-gatherer dispersal